

caged with 2 viruliferous green leaf-hoppers (GLH) *Nephotettix virescens* Distant), Hyderabad ecotype, per tiller for 18-h inoculation feeding at 30, 45, and 60 d after sowing (DAS).

Inoculated plots were surrounded by 1.5-m-high nylon screen to restrict vector movement. Infected plants were marked to estimate spread of infection in the field.

TN1 and IR8 cages with GLH were

100% RTV-infected at all inoculation stages. Symptom expression was delayed by 5-20 d in plots inoculated at different growth stages (Table 1). At 30 DAS, 59% of TN1 plants and 15% of IR8 plants were infected. Sixty-day inoculation gave 2% infection in TN1 and 1% in IR8 (Table 2). Saket-4 did not have external RTV symptoms. Recovery tests in glass-house and field conditions from 25 Saket-4 plants caged with GLH showed

Table 2. Percent RTV-infected plants, Bihar, India.

Cultivar	Infected plants (%) at indicated DAS		
	30 DAS	45 DAS	60 DAS
TN1	59	19	2
IR8	15	4	1
Saket-4	0	0	0

negative transmission, thus confirming its RTV resistance. □

New methods to detect seedborne

Trichoconiella padwickii

S. A. Shetty and H. S. Shetty, *Applied Botany Department, University of Mysore, Mysore 570006, India*

Stack burn disease of rice caused by *Trichoconiella padwickii* (Ganguly) Jain is an important seedborne disease. Some ways of detecting the fungus are the standard blotter method, modified blotter method at pH 4, potato dextrose agar, deep freeze method, and guaiacol agar method. We have developed a new, macroscopic method of detecting *T. padwickii* on rice seeds and a new modified blotter method.

In the macroscopic method, rice seeds were boiled in distilled water under 15 psi for 20 min. The extract was filtered through cheese cloth to fill 1 litre. Agar was added to the extract and sterilized for 15 min. The proportion of rice extract and agar was adjusted to 40:4, 40:20, 80:4, and 80:20. The numbers 40 and 80 indicate the weight (g) of seed used to get the extract; 4 and 20 indicate the weight of agar in 1,000 ml of extract. An antibiotic, Ambistryn-S (0.5 g), was added after sterilization. Twenty ml of this medium was poured into each petri plate. Ten rice seeds were sown equidistantly in each petri plate. The plates were incubated in laboratory conditions (diffused light, 25±2°C); near ultraviolet light (NUV)/darkness (12h/12h) cycles at 22±1°C; or in complete darkness (22±1°C). *T. padwickii* colonies were counted 10 d later.

In the modified blotter method, blotter discs were immersed in rice extract obtained by boiling 40 g rice seed

Percentage of incidence of *T. padwickii* by different seed health testing methods.

Seed health testing method	Incidence ^a (%) in given sample number				Mean (%)
	1	2	3	4	
Standard blotter method	8	10	24	42	21 d
Modified blotter method at pH 4	12	16	38	44	27 c
Potato dextrose agar	18	14	6	36	19 d
Guaiacol agar	40	22	52	46	40 b
Blotter immersed in paddy extract	25	30	42	68	41 b
Deep freeze method	23	24	39	43	32 c
Paddy extract agar (40:20)	27	40	76	51	48 a

^a Treatment means followed by the same letter are not significantly different by Duncan's multiple range test (P=0.05) after arc sine transformation.

in 1 litre of distilled water. The seeds were placed on the blotter in petri plates and the plates were incubated under 12 h/12 h cycles of NUV and darkness at 22±1°C. In the next 24 h, the plates were incubated at -20°C, then were subjected to NUV/darkness cycles for 5 more days.

Rice extract agar medium developed in our laboratory induced maximum expression (48%) of seedborne *T. padwickii* and thus was superior to all other methods (see table). The blotter immersed in rice extract also influenced good expression (41%) of the fungus on seeds.

The rice extract agar medium around *T. padwickii*-infected seeds turned pink on the 4th d when incubated under laboratory conditions and NUV/darkness cycles. Neither the mycelia nor the spores were colored.

Most high yielding rice varieties are susceptible to stack burn disease. The association of the fungus with the seed favors early seedling infection. In routine seed health testing, a macroscopic method for identifying *T. padwickii* is important because it is simple, reliable, and quick. □

Antagonistic effect of dhaincha on survival of *Rhizoctonia solani* f. sp. *sasakii*

A. K. Roy, *Regional Agricultural Research Station, Assam Agricultural University, Diphu 782460, Assam, India*

Survival of sclerotia of *R. solani* Kühn f. sp. *sasakii* Exner, the sheath blight fungus of rice, was found to vary with vegetation adjacent to rice, and particularly when near dhaincha *Sesbania*

aculeata Fawcett and Rendle, a green manure plant. We studied the effect of the common monocotyledonous weeds *Eleusine indica* (L.) Gaertn. and *Dactyloctenium aegyptium* (L.) Beauv. on *R. solani* incidence.

Plantlets of the weeds and seedlings of Pusa 2-2 1 were transplanted on 17 Aug 1982 in 25-cm-diam clay pots containing rice field soil. Eighteen days later, sclerotia of the fungus grown on sterilized rice grains were mixed with